

Category	Subcategory	Concept	Code	Description	Number of references	Examples
Reasons	Technology-related reasons	Complexity of patches	Patch interdependencies	The software, hardware, and firmware interdependencies. The dependencies consisting in the source code (functions, library), versions and legacy software.	30	[Subject - Software version issues on the system [EPAS 17.3] to resolve] 24/1/19 - 47 Office patches on servers [s1-6] (multi-languages and x32 and x64 bit versions) and 7 Visual Studio-related security patches having errors while testing. 6/2/19 - A ticket raised to investigate Visual Studio patches and manually apply if required. - EMR, Issue ID 9
			Faulty patches	Unknown errors during patch testing, deployment, and post-deployment arising from faulty patches.	12	[Subject - [Server s1] non-functional after patching] 30/10/18 - Org A raised a support case to the [vendor v1] as the server was left in an unusable state with no communication post-patching. 4/4/19 - No further update regarding the support case. - Win, Issue ID 6
			Extensive monitoring for faulty patch fixes	Issue kept open and under monitor until the practitioners confirm that the patch poses no unanticipated adverse effects.	8	[Subject - Patch deployment error at the [server s1]] 13/12/19 - Workaround applied and timings were all good. Keep open till January run for confirmation. - EMR, Issue ID 35
			Patch heterogeneity	Diverse set of patch types increasing the complexity.	5	[Subject - Type 4a vs Type 4 for .NET patches] 28/6/19 - Confirm if all servers have moved to Type 4 vs 4A - all needs to be Type 4 with .NET patching as it is -2 months behind (Pre-Prod, Prod) 12/7/19 - Miscommunication regarding patch types 4a and 4. From July onwards Type 4A in previous format will be defunct and Type 4A profile will be used for Type 4. Net-2 months. 9/8/19 - Type 4A is now named Type 4EMR. [P1-AT1] will send out email to advise wider audience. Item to close. - EMR, Issue ID 24
			Increasing rate of patch release	A large number of patches and patch types.	2	[Subject - PreProd and Prod of [T1] to be patched monthly and in separate machine group] 22/2/19 - Org A considering going bi-monthly with PreProd and Prod to keep up with patches. Then moving monthly after confidence is built around for .NET patching 04/04 - Team [T1] still considering the patch cycles and windows for the PreProd and Prod [T1] servers. Various options were requested and were put out in slides for their consideration- T&M apply as outside standard patching methods. - EMR, Issue ID 2
		Lack of accuracy	Lack of accuracy in the output of current tools - missing vulnerabilities in scans, omitting patches during patch deployment.	9	[Subject - Issues with IE patches] 7/8/19 - [...] The Windows update is showing zero missing patches but the [patch deployment tool] is showing 15 missing patches related to IE. [P1-AT2] to raise a support case for Microsoft account manager attention. - EMR, Issue ID 35	
		Limitations of current tools	Lack of scalability	Lack of scalability to handle diverse types of patches and their features.	3	[Subject - 2019 SHA-2 Code Signing Support requirement for Windows and WSUS] 8/3/19 - The patch team following MS release dates for those required updates and will apply to affected OS - win2008R2 SP1 & SP2. 12/3/19 - MS released stand alone security updates: KB4474419 and KB4490628 released to introduce SHA-2 code sign support for Win2008R2 SP1. Will be applied with March cycle to affected servers. 3/5/19 - Excluded against 2008 servers as the tool doesn't support it, [B-T1] working in reports on how it can be applied in near future in May. - EMR, Issue ID 24
			Functionality limitations	Functional incapacities in the tools.	7	[Subject - Additional reboot required for .NET patching] 7/2/20 - Investigation is needed around the number of required reboots for EMR patching and window requirements as a result if more reboots are required. A new process needs to be fleshed out when patching is postponed to accommodate the identification of the number of reboots required. - EMR, Task ID 35
			Troubleshooting	Troubleshooting the issues, unknown errors during and post-deployment and faulty patches.	23	[Subject - Issues with patch installation at [server s1]] 17/4/19 - Installed patches reverting and some patches not getting installed, need further investigation. 3/5/19 - [P1-BT1] ran troubleshooting, no success. Need to raise a support case with Microsoft for advice. - Win, Issue ID 20
		Need of human intervention	Manual patch deployment	Manual patch deployment during complex, erroneous, or business-critical patch installations.	17	[Subject - [Hospital h1] patching stage 3 on 27th November] 18/10/19 - Patching needs to be moved to OOB due to the change freeze from 15th November to 3rd December. 31/10/19 - [P1-BT1] team putting in significant amounts of work, like 15-20 hours per month, to redo the schedules on custom dates each time the deployments move off standard windows. - EMR, Task ID 30
	Decision approvals need thorough assessment of patch impact		Thorough assessment of the impact on multiple aspects to avoid breakdowns.	10	[Subject - Decision on pre-Download of patches for [A-T1]] 29/11/19 - Pre-download to be reverted, no Pre-Download going forward until we can confirm no impact on windows. - EMR, Issue ID 38	
	Manual configurations		Manual configurations based on the organisation needs.	6	[Subject - Decision on pre-Download of patches for [A-T2]] 31/10/19 - [P1-AT2] raised issue, Org B has configured 2nd job 2 hours into the window that rescans for missing patches and conducts a second cycle/post-reboot if required. No issues experienced in October to our knowledge, seeking client feedback. 1/11/19 - [P2-AT2] will check how many servers needed the 2nd reboot and configure accordingly. - Win, Issue ID 38	
	Coordination delays		Delays in obtaining approval	Delays in decision approvals as they had to go through multiple teams (or levels).	37	[Subject - IE version upgrade approval required] 7/9/18 - quote now with [A-T2] team to approve. 3/5/19 - [P1-AT4] to follow up with [P2-AT2] on the status of this. 10/5/19 - [P1] following up, still waiting for approval. - Win, Task ID 1
			Lack of awareness of task progression	Lack of awareness of task progression between teams and organisations.	22	[Subject - Need Service Packs updated to resolve software version incompatibility.] 31/8/18 - Not sure if [A-T1] team has raised Non-Standard Service Request (NSSR) ticket to upgrade 32-bit clients that are lower than IE8. 14/9/18 - Well, [P1-AT1] must know but he's not at the meeting, I'm not sure about it. - Win, Task ID 2
			Lack of understanding of roles and responsibilities	Lack of understanding of shared roles and responsibilities between teams.	6	[Subject - Investigation of post-deployment issue] 18/10/19 - [P1-BT1] says Org B should not be accountable for apps that don't start correctly. 31/10/19 - Decided that Org A or third-party vendor X should be fixing this error, Org B should not be accountable for application problems. - EMR, Issue ID 26
			Poor communication and information misinterpretation	Lack of communication and misinterpretation of communication creating delays as it creates the need to constantly follow up to get responses.	5	[Subject - Cluster-based patching (Type 4a vs Type 4 .NET patches)] 12/7/19 - miscommunication regarding Types 4a and 4. 9/8/19 - Type 4a is now named Type 4EMR. [P1-AT1] to send out email to advise wider audience. - EMR, Issue ID 18
			Missing information due to overload of emails	Misled emails resulting in delays in passing information on time.	2	[Subject - 2008 patching in Week 2] 1/4/21 - Check emails for update KB5000851. The plan had been already emailed to the teams. - EMR, Issue ID 5
			Delays in obtaining customers' approval	Delays in obtaining customers' approval for patch deployment.	14	[Subject - Request to change patch window of [s1] server] 10/5/19 - currently set to 0000-0300, but the full backup of the server happening during this window causes slowness and issues with patching. Suggest changing the window to 0600-0900. [P1-AT2] checking on the status with business approval. 14/6/19 - [P1-AT2] to follow up as no response from the business. - Win, Task ID 19
			Delays in coordinating with vendors for support	Delays in coordinating with vendors for support cases.	12	[Subject - Patch deployment issue - file validation errors in [s1] server] 25/2/19 - [Vendor v1] case [n] - number of fixes suggested, completed last tests on server [s1], still no fix found. 3/5/19 - awaiting full response from [Vendor v1], investigations still underway. - Win, Issue ID 17
			Administrative overhead of coordinating with multiple customers	Administrative overhead of coordinating with multiple customers for pre and post-patching verification.	3	[Subject - Verify client email contact for the task [T1]] 27/2/19 - Provided email contact gives an error message stating that the email is restricted. So [Org B] has altered the special instructions to send emails to [P1] until sorted. 1/3/19 - Org A to contact the client and verify the client's email address. - Win, Issue ID 14

s	People-related reasons	Delegation delays due to conflicts of task ownership	Delegation delays due to conflicts of task ownership with other third-party vendors because of lack of accountability.	3	[Subject – Investigation into SRM services not starting after patching] 31/10/19 - SRM process instructions were added for manual checks and run in October. Org B should not be accountable for apps that don't start correctly. SRM Prod boxes don't seem to be doing this, [A-T1][Vendor V1] should be fixing this at right level, Org B should not be accountable for application problems. - Win, Issue ID 36		
		Input requirement delays	Delays in delivering reports	Delays in delivering the reports such as the vulnerability scan reports.	16	[Subject – Awaiting reports on missing patches on EPAS] 24/1/19 – [P1-AT1] waiting for his request on a monthly report in missed patches - compliance report. Org B to organise and send weekly group reports for missed patches + monthly compliance report. Will consider also list of January released patches required on each server to be produced and communicated. - EMR, Issue ID 10	
			Delays in delivering patch schedule information	Delays in providing information about patch cycle changes, patch windows, server lists and organisational schedule changes like change freeze delaying planning and execution of patch deployment.	15	[Subject - Scheduling Out-Of-Band (OOB) patching for exempted servers] 14/6/19 - An email sent to [P1-AT2] asking for patch window information, pending response. 28/6/19 - A follow-up email was sent to [P1-AT2] as no information was received. 26/7/19 - The patch window is still pending. - Win, Issue ID 22	
			Delays in providing team requirements	Delays in providing team requirements for patching tasks.	4	[Subject - SQL Security Patching] 1/5/19 - No update since 17/4. Seeking confirmation on whether this is still a requirement from us [BT1]. - Non-Win, Issue ID 1	
			Delays in patch release by vendors	Delays in the patch release.	11	[Subject - Investigation of missing patches from March patch run] 1/4/21 - OOB investigation results. Microsoft patch releases on patch Tuesday included listing KB5000803 (also applies to KB5000851 and KB5000853) but the patch was not available to download through [tool T1] until the 16th March. This patch also had a pre-requisite KB5001078 released in Feb that was also released late after Feb patch Tuesday. - EMR, Issue ID 54	
			Delays in providing input for support cases	Delays in receiving vendor's support for support cases.	8	[Subject - New zero-day vulnerability warning] 12/6/20 - Monitor Microsoft patch release for critical vulnerability identified on [T1] servers. Font Type 1 expected as a zero-day soon, full report not available yet. 24/7/20 - No update from Microsoft. - EMR, Task ID 43	
		Failures due to poor planning and execution	Missing patch pre-requisites during installation	Missing patch pre-requisites such as registry changes, GPO configuration and installation of preparation packages. As a result, errors in patch deployment.	1	[Subject -IE version upgrades resulting in additional patches] 1/5/20 - Review status of the IE patching after the current patching run. Will generate status report from [tool T1] now as the patching run is complete. [P1-AT5] to also run a new report. 15/5/20 - Found 3 outstanding servers with patches to be applied for IE. [P2-AT1] to review the list of vulnerabilities from [P3-AT5] to confirm 12/6/20 - 3 vulnerabilities identified under a new yet to be created GPO. [P4-BT1] scheduling the implementation of this. 24/07 - IE patches up to date, 0 missing patches. But keep under observation for one more patch cycle please. [P4-BT1] doing a final scan in relation to IE patching. Item can close. - EMR, Issue ID 57	
			Inaccurate estimates of patch windows	Inaccurate predictions of timing of patch installations.	3	[Subject - Execution exceeding the patch window] 31/5/17 - Only 72.9% of scheduled patch deployments were completed as of 11.20 am. Two further windows to be raised to ensure the appropriate length of time is scheduled due to unknown 2016 updates that were required to be implemented, first window is 1st June 8 am to 12 pm. - Win, Task ID 4	
			Incomplete patch deployment	Patch deployment task left incomplete, such as required rebooting not completed.	5	[Subject - 2008 Critical patches from March] 16/4/21 – Server [s1] is the last remaining EMR 2008 server with missing patches. 30/4/21 – The last outstanding server is being tracked separately; item can close. - EMR, Issue ID 56	
			Inadequate post-patch deployment verification	Failing to monitor the status of patch deployment tasks.	6	[Subject - [Server s1] post-patching functionality issues] 8/10/19 - [Server s1] has not shut down properly during the patch window which caused the printers to be unavailable for [customer c1]. It needs to move to semi-auto patching for November to monitor. - Win, Issue ID 32	
		Organisation-related reasons	Organisation delays	Delays in getting approval from higher management	Delays in obtaining approval from organisational management for monthly patch schedules and changes in the process.	18	[Subject - RITM for new bespoke solution] 8/10/19 - Approval received from AT1, has been sent across to [P1-AT2] to raise the purchase order. 29/11/19 - The requested item is still with Finance (team) for processing. - EMR, Issue ID 23
				Delays due to changes in company schedules	Delays due to changes in organisation schedules like change freeze, testing plans, and holidays/shot down plans.	13	[Subject - Patching for December 2019] 18/10/19 - OOB for November patching from 4th December instead of December patching. 31/10/19 - EMR patching for December month is off but November Microsoft patches will be applied in the first week of December instead to keep compliance up. - EMR, Issue ID 29
			Capacity limitations	Resource limitations	Insufficient human resources to carry out certain tasks.	24	[Subject - L1TF spectre update] 16/5/19 - Task 0117374 assigned to [P1-BT1] (a senior server engineer) for implementation. 14/6/19 - Task on hold until July due to resource (i.e., P1-BT1) being borrowed by [AT4] team (for another critical task). - Win, Issue ID 21
				Infrastructure limitations	Infrastructure-related limitations leading to performance delays.	11	[Subject - Backup server patching] 24/1/20 - Patching cannot go ahead when the active backup is running. The patch load can impact servers before reboot. Need a window change, proposal to be sent by [P1-BT1] to [P2-AT1]. - EMR, Issue ID 39
				Time limitations	Time-bound limitations, e.g., monthly patch cycles, to progress with the tasks.	5	[Subject - [Server s1] storage failover issue] 7/2/19 - A support case was raised with [vendor v1]. Waiting for the next failure to occur to submit the logs, the next patch run is due in late March. - EMR, Issue ID 33
Service availability restrictions	Inability to allow service downtime from reboots		Organisations' restrictions/inability to allow service downtime from reboots.	13	[Subject - Go-Live for [Hospital h1] on 19th, need to postpone any patching happening on that day] 14/6/19 - OOB to be raised to patch servers - list of impacted servers to be sent to [P1-BT1] from [P2-AT1]. 28/6 - OOB scheduled on the next go-live 24th July. 12/7 - Customer proposing date 7th August. Need to reschedule. - EMR, Issue ID 22		
	Multi reboots requiring longer and additional patch windows		The patch schedules scheduled in out-of-band windows to reduce service disruptions from additional patch windows during business hours.	8	[Subject - [Servers s1 and s2] patching] 26/7/19 - OOB window is needed for the multi reboots to catch up. 9/8/19 - Waiting for the customer's confirmation of the new patch window, pending information from [P1-AT1]. - EMR, Issue ID 20		
	Customer requests to postpone patch deployment schedules		Delays due to accommodating customer requests to delay patch deployment to avoid service interruptions.	4	[Subject - Go-Live for [hospital h1] on 19th July] 12/7/19 - Customer [hospital h1] asking to postpone patching until 7th August. - EMR, Issue ID 16		